

COMPRESSION STRENGTH OF ALIGNED CARBON FIBRE
REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC LAMINATES

R.J. Lee
Polymers & Composite Materials Group,
Harwell Laboratory,
OXON, OX11 0RA,
UK

and

A.S. Trevett
School of Materials Science,
University of Bath,
Claverton Down,
Bath,
AVON, BA2 7AY,
UK.

ABSTRACT

Thermoplastic composites offer many potential advantages when compared with epoxide matrix composites such as improved environmental resistance, increased interlaminar toughness and enhanced damage tolerance. An investigation has recently been made of the compressive strength of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics fabricated by film stacking and by melt impregnation. Comparison with aerospace epoxide systems indicate that polyether ether ketone (PEEK) based laminates have similar compression strengths at room temperature but show a greater strength reduction at elevated temperatures.

INTRODUCTION

The technology of impregnating fibres with thermoplastic resins such as polycarbonates and polysulphones is not new [1], and speciality composite suppliers have been producing thermoplastic composites for some time [2]. However, recent developments within the UK have led to the commercial availability of aligned carbon fibres impregnated in tougher, more chemically resistant thermoplastic resins based on polyether ether ketone (Victrex PEEK), marketed by ICI under the trade name APC2 - Aromatic Polymer Composite [3]. While the APC material may be the most widely publicised material at the moment other polymer manufacturers are following suit. Phillips Petroleum are marketing a range of polyphenylene sulphide (Ryton PPS) composites [4]. Du Pont are exploiting thermoplastic composites based on their newly developed J-polymer [5] and General Electric polymers are indirectly supplying polyether imide (Ultem PEI) based composites. Atochem [6] are also supplying tows of glass or carbon fibres impregnated in a polyamide matrix using a powder impregnation route. Reviews of thermoplastic composites technology have been recently published by McMahon

[7] and by Cattenach and Cogswell [8].

Previous work [9] on pre-production [0,90] carbon/PEEK laminates indicated that the compressive strength was approximately 30% lower than carbon/epoxide material. Some of this shortfall was ascribed to kinks in the woven reinforcement of the PEEK composite initiating local fibre buckling. The shear modulus and compressive yield stress of PEEK resin (1.22 GPa and 95 MPa respectively) are both less than those of epoxide resins used in aerospace structures (typically 1.42 GPa and greater than 150 MPa). This might result in a reduction in matrix dominated mechanical properties and in particular the unidirectional compression strength.

The current work describes the selection of a suitable test method for measuring compression strength and includes the Celanese compression fixture (ASTM D3410-82) and an end loaded compression jig developed originally by NASA Langley [10]. Testing procedures and sources of experimental error were evaluated in terms of end constraint, instability effects and failure modes.

The materials examined cover a range of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic laminates fabricated by both the film stacking and the melt impregnation routes obtained from a number of commercial sources. An aerospace standard epoxide resin system, XA-S/Fibredux 914C, was also examined for comparison purposes together with a unidirectional filament wound panel of XA-S carbon fibres in MY750 epoxide resin.

MATERIALS STUDIED

Reinforced thermoplastic panels, 300 mm square and 2 mm thick, were obtained from ICI plc using their direct melt impregnation route and from Specmat Ltd. using the film stacking (solvent impregnation) technique described in British Patent GB 1 570 000 (1980). Unidirectional panels of XA-S/Fibredux 914C were compression moulded by Fothergill Rotorway Ltd. and a unidirectional panel of XA-S in MY750 epoxide resin was filament wound at Harwell for comparison purposes.

After manufacture the laminates were visually inspected to ensure that they were of suitable quality, and a volume fraction measurement was made. Fibre volume fractions were nominally 60%, although the APC1 and film stacked carbon/polyether sulphone (PES) were in the range 50-55%. Details of the materials investigated are given in Table 1.

COMPRESSION TEST METHOD

Compression strength is one of the more difficult intrinsic properties to measure as the results are often dependent on loading geometry and test conditions. To achieve accurate strength measurements special loading fixtures and specimens are essential to overcome three basic problems:

- specimen buckling
- 'brooming' of ends of solid column specimens; and
- axial misalignment.

TABLE 1
Materials evaluated in present work

Material	Fabrication route	Supplier	Processing condition
Carbon/PEEK (APC1)	Melt impregnation	ICI)
Carbon/PEEK (APC2)) 380°C/30 min
Glass/PEEK*)
Carbon/PES*			350°C/30 min
Carbon/PES	Film stacking	Specmat	240°C/30 min
Carbon/914C epoxide	Compression moulded	Ciba-Geigy	170°C/60 min 190°C/240 min+
Carbon/MY750 epoxide	Filament wound	Harwell	100°C/240 min 160°C/240 min+

*Experimental material

Buckling can in principle be overcome by ensuring that the column length is less than the critical Euler buckling length defined by the following equation:

$$P_c = \frac{K\pi^2 EI}{\ell^2} \quad (1)$$

where E is compression Young's modulus, I is the moment of inertia in the thin direction, ℓ is the column length and K is a constraint factor ranging from 4 for clamped ends to 1 for free ends.

A further consideration when dealing with unidirectional composites is their relatively low ratio of shear to axial modulus (~ 0.04 compared with ~ 0.31 for metals) giving rise to further significant reduction in Euler buckling load. The corrected load is given by [11]:

$$P_{(\text{corrected})} = \frac{P_c}{\left(1 + \frac{nP_c}{AG}\right)} \quad (2)$$

where $n = 1.2$ for rectangular columns, A is the cross-sectional area, G is the composite shear modulus and P_c is the Euler buckling load.

Axial misalignment is extremely important as it will introduce a bending moment causing strain divergence on either face. An eccentricity of 2.5% of the laminate thickness (0.05 mm for a 2 mm laminate) has been shown to reduce the apparent strength to 87% of the ultimate value [12]. To reduce this effect requires well controlled bondline thickness for the end tabs, and in some cases shims have to be inserted into the testing machine to ensure that the plattens are parallel.

In the current work two comparison test fixtures were used:

- (1) a Celanese jig (ASTM D3410-82) using a range of gauge lengths from 12.5 to 3 mm; and
- (2) an end-loaded compression fixture [10].

Figure 1 shows test fixtures with representative samples.

Figure 1. Compression test fixtures: (a) Celanese (ASTM D3410) fixture; and (b) end-loaded fixture.

PROCEDURE

The background to compression testing of plane composite bars using the Celanese jig for quality control has been described by Hancox [13]. In the current work specimens $140 \times 6.35 \times 2$ mm were cut from panels using a well aligned diamond cutter mounted on a milling machine. Profiled GRP end tabs were bonded onto the coupons after light abrasion and degreasing. Specimens used for temperatures up to 50°C were bonded with Redux 410 NA room temperature curing epoxide and the remainder were bonded with Araldite 2007. Problems encountered during the higher temperature tests (150°C) necessitated using etched duralumin end tabs. Occasionally end tabs debonded from the PEEK specimens and the corresponding results were discarded. Later it was found that a 30 second etch in warm (40°C) chromic/sulphuric acid solution gave satisfactory bonds.

In some cases strain gauges were bonded onto either side of the specimen to monitor bending resulting from load eccentricity. Some strain divergence was evident for the 12.5 mm gauge length specimens. As the gauge length was reduced to 6 mm measured strengths increased by as much as 25%.

End-loaded compression testing was carried out at RARDE (Christchurch) using thickness waisted specimens. Since the load was introduced into the specimen ends, bonded end tabs were not required. The reduced section thickness was ~ 1.6 – 1.8 mm and the radius of curvature was 125 mm. In general an average of 10 strength measurements was recorded.

RESULTS

Figure 2 shows average compression results, together with standard deviations, obtained from the Celanese jig using a gauge length of 12.5 mm. Both PES matrix composites gave similar mean strengths of 615 MPa which were significantly lower than the epoxide or PEEK composites. Average strength values for carbon/PEEK (APC1) compared favourably with the MY750 data (1044 compared with 1023 MPa) although both were lower than Fibredux 914C (1120 MPa).

Figure 2. Celanese compression results (12.5 mm gauge length).

The effect of reducing the gauge length of the XA-S/914C specimen was investigated and results are shown in Table 2. It became evident that compression strength increased as the gauge length was reduced to 6.0 mm and this was adopted as a standard gauge length during subsequent testing. Remaining samples together with additional APC2 and glass/PEEK materials were tested and values obtained are shown in Figure 3.

TABLE 2
Effect of gauge length on compression strength for XA-S/914C

Gauge length	Compressive strength (MPa)	Data range (MPa)
12.5	1120 ± 66	991-1235
6.0 (1st attempt)	1409 ± 206	1085-1650
6.0 (repeat)	1533 ± 41	1462-1561
3.0	1405 ± 40	1346-1459

Figure 3. Celanese compression results (6 mm gauge length)

Table 3 shows the results obtained from the end-loaded compression fixture using thickness-profiled 10 mm wide specimens which had a gauge length of approximately 15 mm. The highest individual strength values are similar (~ 1275 - 1294 MPa) whereas some low values below 1000 MPa were observed for APC2. The possible cause of scatter with APC2 could be due to fibre waviness which was more evident than the epoxide although difficult to quantify.

TABLE 3
End-loaded compression results using thickness-profiled specimens

Material	Compression strength (MPa)	Data range (MPa)
XA-S/914C	1231 ± 61	1150-1294
APC1	1192 ± 24	1165-1210
APC2	1113 ± 136	910-1275

Figure 4 illustrates the effect of elevated temperature on compression strength where it can be seen that strength reduction is more marked for the APC1 composites.

Figure 4. Effect of test temperature on compression strength.

DISCUSSION

The variation of compression strength with unsupported gauge length is similar to earlier results reported by Hancox [13]. In that work, attempts to interpret the curves on the basis of buckling theory were not completely successful. The data could only be fitted using assumptions that either end constraints changed with gauge length or that the strut was eccentrically loaded. Hancox's conclusion was that compression strength of a unidirectional carbon fibre composite at room temperature is not governed by fibre buckling but is related to the ultimate fibre strength.

Port [14] observed that compression strengths for Toray T300/914 reported by a German aerospace company were as high as 1800 MPa with low data scatter. As these data were obtained from a thicker specimen with a reduced gauge length of approximately 4 mm initial reaction was that because of the very short gauge length a certain amount of Poisson expansion was being restricted and hence a lower energy mode of failure (e.g. longitudinal splitting) was being suppressed.

Sinclair and Chamis [15] recently reported an investigation of compression behaviour using the IITRI test method. In common with our experience some strain gauged specimens showed strain divergence on either face using the standard 12.7 mm gauge length suggesting possible instability

effects. Partial end tab debonding was also reported, and has also been observed in some of the failed specimens. This might be responsible for increasing the effective gauge length and reducing the degree of end constraint.

Woolstencroft and co-workers [16] examined the cause of variability of results for different compression test methods using Nastran finite element analysis. Their results indicated the importance of achieving uniformity in stress distribution in the longitudinal direction and of minimising transverse compressive stresses which will inhibit splitting. In their work the RAE specimen gave the optimum performance in terms of high mean strength (1400 MPa) together with a low coefficient of variation ($C_v = 2.0\%$).

In the present work, attempts to compare failure modes with measured properties has met with limited success, one of the basic problems being that considerable post-fracture damage is produced as the two fracture surfaces are created. Visual inspection of fractured specimens revealed a limited number of failure modes. All the film stacked carbon/PES specimens failed mostly at a point one-third of the distance along the gauge length and there was minimal splitting or delamination. The fracture path tended to be mainly perpendicular to the applied load and inclined at 45° to the thickness direction. Evidence of slight end tab debonding was present and this tended to be associated with lower strength specimens. The melt impregnated PES material failed in a slightly different way without showing any significant difference in strength values. Here the fracture surfaces tended to be adjacent to one end tab and there was also more of a tendency for the material to split, typical lengths being in the region of 3-5 mm.

The APC1 specimens showed much more extensive splitting and delamination. Whether this occurred before or after failure was difficult to determine. Partial end tab debonding was much more common (lengths typically 5 mm although occasionally much longer) and in some cases end tabs were completely debonded. The majority of failures tended to be adjacent to the end tabs with the fracture plane inclined at an angle of $\sim 70^\circ$ relative to the fibre direction. Split lengths extended over the whole gauge length whereas delaminations tended to be limited to 2-3 mm.

Both epoxide matrix composites showed similar fracture behaviour, although the carbon/914C was approximately 10% stronger than the filament wound MY750. Fracture planes, again inclined at $\sim 70^\circ$ to the longitudinal direction, seldom occurred mid-way along the gauge length but often appeared near one-quarter to one-third of the way along the span. The presence of splits and delaminations tended to be similar in magnitude and extent to those observed in the PEEK-based laminates.

Differences observed in compression strength between APC1 and APC2 (16% improvement) could be explained by variations in fibre volume fraction (approximately 15% increase) despite the fact that a different source of carbon fibre is used in APC2. The strength of the first glass/PEEK was quite surprising especially as one individual sample failed at 2100 MPa. Another specimen was loaded to over 1800 MPa before all four end tabs debonded, and showed no signs of visible damage. The fracture mode of glass/PEEK was quite different from the carbon reinforced material in that the whole gauge length had multiple splits and delaminations. It was not certain why the first batch of material was so strong whereas the second batch gave values which were much lower.

A recurring problem in compression testing is the variety in failure modes and the scatter in results which can be caused by a number of factors. This includes non-uniformity of stress application and poor specimen design. The first attempt to measure the compression strength of XA-S/914C specimens of 6.0 mm gauge length resulted in a mean strength of 1409 MPa with a coefficient of variation (C_v) of 14%. When the test was repeated at a later date with new material the mean value increased to 1533 MPa with a C_v of approximately 3%.

Unidirectional compression strength data may be of limited value for design purposes partly because many designs are controlled by geometric instability rather than material strength. It is also not clear how samples under test, which are small compared with real structures, represent the behaviour of bulk material. Such measurements do, however, give a valuable indication of developments in materials properties and potential design values.

CONCLUSIONS

A number of commercially produced reinforced thermoplastic laminates have been evaluated and compared with two epoxide resin systems produced by compression moulding and filament winding. Polyether sulphone (PES) composites are relatively poor in compression (~ 615 MPa) compared with other materials, and this can be ascribed to the low matrix shear modulus (~ 0.94 MPa).

Unidirectional carbon/PEEK composites (APC2) gave similar compression strength to the epoxide composites at room temperature (~ 1400 MPa) but showed a greater strength reduction at elevated temperatures.

The end loaded compression fixture gave lower values of compression strength than the 6 mm gauge length Celanese jig possibly because of the reduced section thickness combined with the longer gauge length. The mean value for the epoxide system was 1231 MPa and for the APC2 material was 1131 MPa.

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